

Thermodynamic Metal-Ligand Stability Constants of Pd(II), Pt(II), Rh(III) and Fe(III) Complexes of Biuret

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Potentiometric studies on complexes of biuret with Pd(II), Pt(II), Rh(III) and Fe(III) at different ionic strengths ($\mu=0.2M, 0.15M, 0.10M$ and $0.05M$) have been carried out at room temperature $25(\pm 0.02)^\circ$. The Calvin-Bjerrum pH titration technique as used by Irving and Rossotti has been applied to determine the dissociation constants of biuret and successive stability constants of metal complexes. The covalent nature and π -bonding of metal-ligand have been discussed in detail.

BIURET (BT) has been proved a great potential donor ligand¹⁻⁴. In our earlier publication⁵, stabilities of some bivalent metal complexes of biuret have been studied. The stereochemical studies on platinum metal complexes with biuret have been reported⁶. For rational applications of biuret in analytical chemistry it is desirable to have a quantitative knowledge of stabilities of their complexes with various metal ions. In the present communication the stability constants of Pd(II), Pt(II), Rh(III) and Fe(III) complexes of the BT is reported. The metal-ligand stability constants have been determined by following the Bjerrum⁸-Calvin⁹ titration technique as adopted by Irving and Rossotti⁷.

Experimental

Solution of palladium(II), platinum(II), rhodium(III) and iron(III) were prepared from analytical grade reagent. Fresh solid biuret (BDH) was weighed out for every titration.

The experimental procedure involved the potentiometric titration against standard (0.01M) sodium hydroxide of the three mixtures. Mixture I-Perchloric acid (0.02M); Mixture(II) Perchloric acid (0.02M)+BT (0.01M) and Mixture(III) Perchloric acid (0.02M)+BT(0.01M)+metal solution (0.005M). Such that the concentration of common ingredients were identical in different cases. Sodium perchlorate was added to maintain the different ionic strengths ($\mu=0.2M, 0.15M, 0.10M$ and $0.05M$). The final volume of the mixture was adjusted to 50 ml. The nitrogen was passed through the solution to exclude carbon dioxide.

pH measurements were done by Philips pH meter using glass calomel electrode assembly at constant temperature $25(\pm 0.02)$.

Results and Discussion

The data of stability constants of the biuret complexes with Pd(II), Pt(II), Rh(III) and Fe(III) are summarized in Table 1.

Biuret is known to act as bidentate ligand and form complex with metal ions. The complex formation is believed to take place by replacement of $-NH_2$ hydrogen by metals.

The titration curves obtained for Pd(II), Pt(II), Rh(III) and Fe(III) with biuret were similar to that reported earlier⁵ for divalent 3dⁿ transition metal ions. The value of $n_{\bar{H}}$, n^- and pL (where $n_{\bar{H}}$ = average number of proton attached to the ligand, n^- =ligand number or average number of ligand molecules or ions per molecules of metal and pL = free ligand exponent) were calculated from the shift in pH titration curves by using Irving and Rossotti method⁷. The protonation constants (pK) value for the biuret at different ionic strengths were obtained from the formation curves drawn between $n_{\bar{H}}$ and pH. The successive stability constants ($\log K_1$ and K_2) of the metal chelates at different ionic strengths ($\mu=0.2M, 0.15M, 0.10M$ and $0.05M$) were directly read from their formation curves which were obtained by plotting n^- against pL . The values are given in Table 1. Fig. 1 shows the formation curves for BT complexes with Pd(II), Pt(II), Rh(III) and Fe(III) at ionic strength 0.2M. Similar curves were obtained for ionic strength 0.15M, 0.10M, 0.05M. The thermodynamic dissociation constant and stability constants at $\mu=0$ were obtained by determination at various ionic strengths followed by extrapolation to zero ionic strength¹⁰. The sum of $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ at $\mu=0$ gives the value of $\log \beta$ at $\mu=0$. The $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ values (Table 1) for metal complexes examined here, on comparison show the following order :

From the above relation it is found that stability constant increases with atomic number. The thermodynamic stability constant $\log \beta$ ($\mu=0$) of the complexes of above mentioned metal ions with BT have been plotted against i/r (Fig. 2). Data of crystal ionic radii (r) were taken from Weast¹¹. It is observed that metal ions more or less show a linear

TABLE 1—STABILITY CONSTANTS AND STANDARD FREE ENERGY CHANGE OF BT-METAL COMPLEXES

Metal ion/ligand BT	log K_1 pK	Ionic strength					Standard free energy change ΔG° (K cal/mole)
		$\mu=0.2M$ 10.25*	$\mu=0.15M$ 10.30	$\mu=0.10M$ 10.45	$\mu=0.05$ 10.50	$\mu=0.0$ 10.57**	
Pd(II)	log K_1	9.80	9.95	10.10	10.25	10.40	-22.53
	log K_2	5.80	5.85	5.95	6.05	6.12	
	log β	15.60	15.60	16.05	16.30	16.52	
	log K_1/K_2	4.0	4.10	4.05	4.20	4.28	
Pt(II)	log K_1	10.80	10.85	10.95	11.15	11.27	-24.18
	log K_2	6.00	6.15	6.20	6.35	6.46	
	log β	16.80	17.00	17.15	17.50	17.73	
	log K_1/K_2	4.80	4.70	4.75	4.80	4.81	
Rh(III)	log K_1	9.50	9.60	9.65	9.75	9.85	-21.80
	log K_2	5.70	5.85	5.90	6.00	6.10	
	log β	15.20	15.45	15.55	15.75	15.95	
	log K_1/K_2	3.80	3.75	3.75	3.75	3.75	
Fe(III)	log K_1	9.25	9.35	9.45	9.60	9.67	-21.20
	log K_2	5.60	5.65	5.75	5.80	5.88	
	log β	14.85	15.00	15.20	15.40	15.55	
	log K_1/K_2	3.65	3.70	3.70	3.70	3.79	

* Value is reported⁹.

** Values calculated by extrapolation of ionic strength.

ΔG° : Standard Free Energy change calculated at $\mu=0$.
log $\beta = \log K_1 K_2$.

FIG. 1 FORMATION CURVES AT $\mu = 0.2M$

FIG. 2 PLOT OF $\log \beta$ ($\mu=0$) AGAINST $\frac{1}{4}$ Cryst.

behaviour and it suggested presence of covalent nature of metal-ligand bond.

The large difference in the values of successive stability constants (log K_1 and log K_2) can be explained by the consideration of the fact that the ions (BT^{-2}) have bigger size and may face steric hindrance while combining with metal ions. Similar behaviour is observed in case of σ bonding ligands like amino acid. Besides $N \rightarrow M$ σ bonding, there exist strong $M \rightarrow N\pi$ interaction due to back donation of electron from metal d_π to vacant delocalized orbitals of biuret. The presence of $M \rightarrow N\pi$ bond has been confirmed by various investigators¹². The presence of such $\pi M-L$ interaction can be explained on the basis of high positive value of log K_1/K_2 . As a tendency of metal ions to take up ligand is proportional to number of vacant site, the ratio between successive constants, to a certain extent is statistically determined⁹. In the present case the value of log K_1/K_2 lies between 3.7 to 4.8 log unit (Table 1) against the statistically determined unit value.

The values of standard free energy change (ΔG°) have been determined at $\mu=0$ using expression

$$\Delta G^\circ = -2.303 RT \log \beta$$

For the complexes probable structure can be represented as

where $M = Pt, Pd, Rh$ and Fe .

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